

A STUDY ON MULTI-AXIS FORCE MEASUREMENT OF POLYMER SKINS USING FBG SENSOR

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1 Introduction

The research related to measure the multi-axial forces such as contact forces and friction forces on the ground has been carried out in the field of tactile sensing devices.

The developed tactile sensors could reproduce a human sensation by measuring only contact forces or a slip by lateral forces. Also, they are very expensive and have low durability due to the use of MEMS technologies or the semiconductor sensor. In order to overcome the disadvantages mentioned above, flexible substrates such as silicone and polymers with embedded fiber-type sensors such as piezoelectric sensors or fiber optic sensors have been studied. In particular, FBG sensors, which have several sensing points on one fiber optic sensor, were very efficient for multi-point sensing.

Therefore, in this study, multi-axial force detection in polymer structures was investigated using embedded FBG sensor for developing a new tactile sensing system.

2 Materials and Testing Methods

2.1 Materials

In this study, Fiber Bragg Grating (FBG) sensors composed of quartz material were used with a diameter of approximately 250 μ m. As a kind of fiber optic sensors, FBG sensors have a feature of changing the refractive index in Bragg grating to reflect specific wavelengths of light. FBG sensors are consisted of light propagating core part, cladding to block external light, and buffer to protect from external shock. Under external loads such as temperature changes and external forces, the Bragg grating is contracted or relaxed, and as the wavelength of the reflected light is changed. Therefore, the external force applied to the sensor can be determined by measuring the wavelength changes.

Table.1 shows the specification of the FBG sensor. As shown in Fig.1, the FBG sensor four Bragg gratings with 10mm of length and 20mm of interval, and wavelengths of each FBG were set by 1520, 1540, 1560, and 1590nm section split.

Epoxy, Polyester and polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) were used for polymer skins and their specification was shown in Table. 2.

2.2 Specimen

In this study, three different specimens with respect to the skin materials were prepared. As shown in Fig.2 plate-type specimens (100 x 100 x 2 mm) were fabricated with arrayed FBG sensors with the interval of 20mm.

Fig. 1. Configuration of FBG sensor

Fig. 2. Schematic configuration of specimens

Fig. 3. represents the fabricating procedure of specimens. First, FBG sensors were installed in the mold along the grooves of the mold edges to prevent damage or injury, and then the mold was assembled. At this time, FBG sensors in the assembly process added grooves to prevent damage or injury. Second, the assembled mold was preheated oven for about 30 minutes, and then the skin materials were poured and cured.

2.3 Test Equipment

In order to evaluate the sensing performance of the contact and frictional forces, testing machine can give the biaxial motion and loading to the specimens. It is difficult for the conventional testing equipment to conduct the multi-axial loading tests a new testing machine was equipped as shown in Fig. 4.

Table 1. FBG sensor specifications

Wavelength range	1510~1590nm
Wavelength tolerance	+/- 0.5nm
Reflectivity	>90%
FWHM	0.2 ~ 0.4nm
Strain range	1000 $\mu\epsilon$
Fiber type	SMF-28 Acrylate Recoating
Strain sensitivity	1.20pm/ $\mu\epsilon$
Temp sensitivity	11pm/ $^{\circ}\text{C}$
Proof test	100Kpsi
Pigtailed length	1m(in each side)
Connector type	FC/APC(optional)
Operating temperature	-20~80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$
Dimensions	145 x 30 x 20 mm
Weight	50g

Table 2. Skin materials

Division		Epoxy	Polyester	PDMS
Resin	Product	YD-115	R-235	SYLGARD-184(a)
Curing agent / Catalyst	Product	G-A0533	MEKPO	SYLGARD-184(b)
Mixing ratio		2:1	100:1	2:1
Curing	Temp. ($^{\circ}\text{C}$)	80	80	80
	Time (Hour)	2	2	3
Manufacturer		Kukdo Chemical	Sewon Hwasung	Dow-Corning

Fig. 3. Fabrication procedure of test specimens

Fig. 4. Biaxial testing equipment

The liner motor (Fig. 4③) was attached to the linear rail for controlling the specimen position and applying frictional forces. Jigs (Fig. 4④) were on the linear rail for installing the specimen. In order to apply the constant contact forces, 5 weights of 10N each were used as shown in Fig. 4①. Voice coil motor (Fig. 4②) was equipped for dynamic contact

Table 3. Testing equipment configuration

Liner motor	Product	LA-3
	Manufacturer	TGG
	Specifications	Speed : 4~40mm/s Load : 50~1200N
Loadcell	Product	CBFSA / LF 1
	Manufacturer	CAS Korea / KOZY International
	Specifications	Load : 300 / 200N
Voice coil motor	Specifications	Load : 100N
Displacement sensor	Product	OD Value
	Manufacturer	RADIAN
	Specification	Displacement : 60~180mm

forces. Contact and friction forces were measured by two miniature loadcells with 200N and 300N capacity assembled at the end of the contact force loading tip and between the linear motor and jigs, respectively. In order to measure the exact position and moving speed of specimens laser displacement sensor (Fig. 4⑤) was mounted at the base block. Details of each part were shown in Table 3.

2.4 FBG sensor analysis

FBG sensors have distributed Bragg reflector in a short segment on the optical fiber that can reflect light with different wavelengths, and physical quantity (length changes) can be detected by measuring the wavelength changes of each Bragg reflector.

In this study, polarization-maintaining optical fibers with two unique polarization axes were used in order to measure the contact forces normal to the tactile sensing area and the frictional force parallel to the tactile sensing area.

Fig.5 shows the typical forms of the measured signals during the experiments. Fig. 5(a) the measured signals under the static contact. Since the static load was applied, maintained for a given time, and then remove, a square type wave signal was observed. The signals were positive if the material was under the tensile deformation, a negative if under the compressive deformation. When the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces were applied, the wavelength changes were also sinusoidal as shown in Fig. 5(b). Fig. 5(c) represents the measured signals when the friction force is applied. When the

loading tip passed on the FBG sensors, the wavelength changes were observed.

The measured wavelength changes were converted to the strain using equation (1).

$$\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B} = K_T\Delta T + K_\varepsilon\Delta\varepsilon \quad (1)$$

K_T and K_ε represent the sensitivity of FBG sensors to the strain and temperature.

In this study, strain can be simplified as equation (2) because the temperature remains constant.

$$\Delta\varepsilon = \frac{\left(\frac{\Delta\lambda_B}{\lambda_B}\right)}{K_\varepsilon} \quad (2)$$

Fig. 5. The typical forms of the measured signals

2.5 Test methods

The purpose of this study is to analyze the magnitude, location, moving direction and load types of the external multi-axial loads based on the sensor's signal, and then determine the information of contact surfaces in real-time.

Since the contact forces and friction forces were applied simultaneously, several variables should be selected before conducting experiments. In this study, considered polymer materials, the magnitude and location of the static contact forces, the magnitude, location and frequency of the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces, and the magnitude, location and moving speed of the frictional forces were selected as the experimental parameters.

In order to investigate the effects of the contact forces, the static and dynamic contact forces were applied on the designated location of the Fig. 6(a).

The magnitude of the contact forces were in the range of 10 ~ 50N, and the distance between the designated locations was 10mm. Frequencies of the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces varied from 1 to 10Hz.

(a) Loading position of static /dynamic contact forces

(b) Moving path of frictional Force

Fig. 6. Loading position and path of contact and frictional forces

The Frictional forces were applied on the indicated lines of the Fig. 6(b), according to distance, Load and moving speed. In these tests, the frictional forces were applied by the friction between the loading tips and the specimens under the contact forces, and the moving speeds of the loading tips were varied from 10 to 40 mm/s.

3 Experimental Results and Discussion

3.1 Static Contact Forces

In Fig. 7, the strain, measured by the FBG sensor 1, with respect to the magnitude of the contact forces and polymer materials is shown when the static contact forces were applied at the location of P1. If the load increases, Epoxy and Polyester deformed compressively, while PDMS tensilely. However, strain changed linearly for all cases.

Fig. 7. The strain measured by the FBG sensor 1, with respect to the magnitude of the contact forces and polymer materials when the static contact forces were applied at the location of P1.

Fig. 8. The measured strains with respect to the distance between the loading position (PE1 – PE5) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials.

Fig. 8 depicts the measured strains with respect to the distance between the loading position (PE1 – PE5) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials. In this case, 10N of the contact force were applied along the direction perpendicular to the FBG sensor 1. As shown in Fig. 8, the compressive strains were observed and the magnitude decreased in the case of epoxy and polyester. However, in the case of PDMS, the measured strain was tensile near the sensor, and then changed to compressive similarly to the cases of epoxy and polyester.

The strains measured at FBG sensor 1 with respect to the loading position of PA1 – PA7 and the polymer materials were shown in Fig. 9. In this case, 10N of the contact forces were applied along the direction parallel to the FBG sensor 1. Strains in epoxy and polyester were monotonically changed from compressive to tensile, while strain changes of

Fig. 9. The measured strains with respect to the distance between the loading position (PA1 – PA7) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials.

Fig.10. The measured strains with respect to the measuring and loading positions when 10N of the static contact force was applied to PDMS along the direction perpendicular to FBG sensor 1.

Fig. 11. The measured strains with respect to the measuring and loading positions when 10N of the static contact force was applied to PDMS along the direction parallel to FBG sensor 1.

PDMS had similar trend with the results of Fig. 8.

Figs. 10 and 11 show the measured strains with respect to the measuring and loading positions when 10N of the static contact force was applied to PDMS along the direction perpendicular and parallel to FBG sensor 1, respectively.

As shown in Fig. 10, the measured strains at FBG sensor 1 (near the loading position) were changed from tensile to compressive. But the measured strains at other FBG sensors were compressive and decreased as the distance between the loading and measuring positions increased. Even though the strain changes at each FBG sensor were different, the magnitude of the strain changes was almost same with the distance between the loading and measuring positions if the distance was larger than 10 mm.

Unlike the results of Fig. 10, the measured strains had sudden changes when the static contact forces were applied near the measuring position. For all FBG sensors, almost zero or slightly compressive strains were observed when the static contact forces were applied far enough away. As the loading position became closer, the compressive strains increased. However, the measured strains were suddenly changed from compressive to tensile when the static contact forces were applied just near each FBG sensors.

3.2 Dynamic Contact Forces

Figs. 12 and 13 show the measured strains with respect to the distance between the loading position (PE1 – PE5, PA1 – PA7) and FBG sensor 1 and the

polymer materials when the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces with 10N magnitude and 1Hz frequency were applied and strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1.

Overall strain changes as shown in Figs. 12 and 13 were similar to those under the static contact forces as shown in Figs. 8 and 9 with the exception of small differences of strain values.

The measured strains at each FBG sensor with respect to the distance between the loading position (PE1 – PE5, PA1 – PA7) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials were shown in Figs. 14 and 15 when the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces with

10N magnitude and 1Hz frequency were applied to PDMS.

Overall strain changes as shown in Figs. 14 and 15 were also similar to those under the static contact forces as shown in Figs. 10 and 11 with the exception of small differences of strain values.

Fig. 16 represent the strain changes with respect to the frequency of the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces with 10N magnitude when the loading and measuring positions were PE1 and FBG sensor 1, respectively. As shown in Fig. 16, it seemed that the dynamic loading frequency didn't affect the strain changes.

Fig. 12. The measured strains with respect to the distance between the loading position (PE1 – PE5) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials when the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces with 10N magnitude and 1Hz frequency were applied and strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1.

The measured strains at each FBG sensor with respect to the distance between the loading position (PE1 – PE5) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials

Fig. 13. The measured strains with respect to the distance between the loading position (PA1 – PA7) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials when the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces with 10N magnitude and 1Hz frequency were applied and strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1.

Fig. 15. The measured strains at each FBG sensor with respect to the distance between the loading position (PA1 – PA7) and FBG sensor 1 and the polymer materials

Fig. 16. The strain changes with respect to the frequency of the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces

3.2 Multi-axial Forces

Figs. 17 – 19 show the measured strains of epoxy, polyester and PDMS with respect to the loading position when the frictional forces with 10mm/s speed moved along Path 1 – 7 under 10N magnitude of the static contact force and the strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1. Negative values of the location mean that the frictional forces were applied at the left side of FBG sensor 1 and vice versa.

When the frictional forces were applied on the epoxy and polyester specimens, which had relatively large Young’s moduli, the measured strains had almost same tendency as shown in Figs. 17 and 18. When the loading tip passed right on the FBG sensor line along Path 1, maximum tensile strains were observed at FBG sensor 1 while those along other paths were slightly changed. However, no strain change was detected when the loading tip was over 10 mm far from the FBG sensor line.

In case of PDMS, which had relatively low Young’s modulus, the maximum tensile strains were observed when the loading tip passed on the FBG sensor line regardless the moving paths. Of course, the maximum values were decreased as the loading path became farther.

When the frictional forces with 10 mm/s speed were applied on PDMS specimens along Path 1 under 10N of the contact force, the measured strain changes of each FBG sensor were shown in Fig. 20. Overall strain tendency was quite similar to the results of Fig. 19. The closer FBG sensor and the loading path was, the larger strain changed.

Fig. 21, which is replotted from Figs. 17 – 19, shows the strain changes of each polymer materials measured at FBG sensor 1 when the frictional forces with 10mm/s speed were applied along Path 1 under 10N of the contact force. All cases had a similar trend as mentioned in the results of Figs. 17 – 19, but the magnitude of the strain changes were different due to the Young’s moduli of each polymer materials.

The effect of the moving speed of the frictional forces on the strain changes was shown in Fig. 22. In this case, the frictional forces were applied on PDMS specimens along Path 1 under 10N of the contact force and the strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1. The maximum tensile strains were increased slightly when the moving speed increased.

Fig. 17. The measured strains of epoxy with respect to the loading position when the frictional forces with 10mm/s speed moved along Path 1 – 7 under 10N magnitude of the static contact force and the strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1.

Fig. 18. The measured strains of polyester with respect to the loading position when the frictional forces with 10mm/s speed moved along Path 1 – 7

Fig. 19 The measured strains of PDMS with respect to the loading position when the frictional forces with 10mm/s speed moved along Path 1 – 7 under 10N magnitude of the static contact force and the strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1.

Fig. 21. The strain changes of each polymer materials measured at FBG sensor 1 when the frictional forces with 10mm/s speed were applied along Path 1 under 10N of the contact force, which is replotted from Figs. 17 – 19.

Fig. 20. The measured strain changes of each FBG sensor when the frictional forces with 10 mm/s speed were applied on PDMS specimens along Path 1 under 10N of the contact force

Fig. 22. The effect of the moving speed of the frictional forces on the strain changes when the frictional forces were applied on PDMS specimens along Path 1 under 10N of the contact force and the strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1.

But there was no difference when the loading tip was over 10mm far from the FBG sensor.

Fig. 23 represents the effect of the magnitude of the frictional forces when the frictional forces were applied on PDMS along Path 1 under the contact forces of 10 – 50N and the strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1. The maximum tensile strains were increased distinguishably when the frictional forces increased.

3.2 Compare contact pressure and Frictional force

Fig. 24, which was replotted from Figs. 8, 12 and 21, represents the comparison between the strain

changes under the uniaxial loads (the static or dynamic contact forces) and the multi-axial loads (the static contact force and friction force). As shown in Fig. 24, the tendencies of the strain changes under the uniaxial and multi-axial loads were similar. In particular, there is a little difference between the static and dynamic contact forces. In addition, the strain changes under both of the contact and friction forces (multi-axial forces) were shifted from those under the uniaxial loads. This was caused by the addition of the frictional forces to the contact forces under the same conditions.

Fig. 23. The effect of the magnitude of the frictional forces when the frictional forces were applied on PDMS along Path 1 under the contact forces of 10 – 50N and the strain changes were measured at FBG sensor 1.

From these results, it can be expected that the contact and friction forces can be separated and the information of the contact surface can be determined by measuring the strain changes using developed tactile sensing structures.

4 Conclusion

In this study, multi-axial force detection in polymer structures was investigated using embedded FBG sensor for developing a new tactile sensing system. Plate-type specimens with three different materials were fabricated with arrayed FBG sensors.

Polymer materials, the magnitude and location of the static contact forces, the magnitude, location and frequency of the sinusoidal dynamic contact forces, and the magnitude, location and moving speed of the frictional forces were selected as the experimental parameters.

As the load increased and the loading position became closer, the strain changes were larger for all materials under both the uniaxial and multi-axial loads. The tendencies of the strain changes of epoxy and polyester were somewhat different from that of PDMS since PDMS had lower hardness and modulus than epoxy and polyester.

The strain changes under the multi-axial loads were similar to those under the uniaxial loads, but the values of the strain changes are different. Therefore, it can be expected that the contact and friction forces can be separated and the information

(a) Epoxy

(b) Polyester

(c) PDMS

Fig. 24. The comparison between the strain changes under the uniaxial loads (the static or dynamic contact forces) and the multi-axial loads (the static contact force and friction force), which was replotted from Figs. 8, 12 and 21.

of the contact surface can be determined by measuring the strain changes using developed tactile sensing structures.

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